

ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS IN THE SYSTEM OF MILITARIZED HIGHER EDUCATION

Kulakhmetov Abdusattor Bakhridinovich
Head of the Department of Legal, Social and Humanitarian Sciences
of Academic Lyceum No. 1 of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the
city of Tashkent, Candidate of Legal Sciences
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It is known that the issue of education and upbringing has been considered as a matter of life and death in the development of humanity. The issue of security also depends on education. Therefore, countries around the world view this issue as a national issue.

Education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time, it is a factor that determines the level of consciousness and its development. Consequently, without changing the education system, it is impossible to change consciousness. Without changing consciousness and thinking, it is impossible to build a free and prosperous society.

In our country, thanks to independence, the issue of education and upbringing has been raised to the level of state policy. A national model of education has been created.

It is no exaggeration to say that the fundamental reform of the education system has become the most important factor and solid foundation for changing the consciousness and worldview of our people, increasing their political and civic activity, and confidence in their future. Our new generation, educated youth, free from all vices of the past, today is becoming the decisive driving force of the democratization and liberalization of our country, its renewal and reliable development.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 16, 2017 No. UP-4958 "On Further Improvement of the Postgraduate Education System" is a vivid confirmation of this point.

Today, special attention is paid to the psychological factors of the development of the education system, increasing the effectiveness of work on preparing for professional activity. The implementation of these complex and important tasks depends on the professional skills of pedagogical staff, the ability to manage the student collective and psychologically influence them. Because... "the professional level of the teaching staff is their special knowledge. In this

ABSTRACT

The article expresses opinions on the specific qualities of increasing the pedagogical and psychological competence of a teacher in the militarized higher education system and the factors of its development.

regard, it is necessary to create an environment that actively promotes the processes of education, spiritual and educational development, and the formation of true values" [6].

In this sense, the pedagogical-psychological competence of a specialist is a unique individual-psychological structure of the individual, which ensures the effectiveness of professional activity in the "human-human" system. It consists of cognitive and practical components, psychological knowledge, professional thinking, practical skills and abilities necessary for establishing interpersonal communication and psychological influence.

In the dictionary of applied psychology, competence is defined as "the ability to be based on deep knowledge and effectively interact with surrounding people in the system of interpersonal relations" [4].

For the successful implementation of pedagogical activity, such personal qualities of a teacher as reflexivity, communicativeness, and cooperation are important and necessary [5].

A number of scientists [1,2,3,8;] supplement the list of the most important professional psychological qualities of a teacher with pedagogical erudition, purposefulness, practical thinking, pedagogical-psychological tact, professional observation, the ability to listen, the ability to make correct decisions in various non-standard situations, psychological forecasting, and psychological-pedagogical reflection. These qualities of a teacher are manifested in harmony with the possession of psychological and pedagogical competence in relation to pedagogical activity.

The components of psychological competence are inextricably linked and form a holistic system of internal (subjective) and external (objective) structures.

Psychological and pedagogical competence of a teacher:

- having information about the individual psychological characteristics of each student, temperament, abilities, strengths and weaknesses of character, level of upbringing, achievements and shortcomings in activity;
- good knowledge of the socio-psychological environment in the team, knowledge of the psychological characteristics of the relationship between the student and the teacher;
- awareness of the most convenient and modern methods of personal education, the ability to use them effectively, possession of skills in introducing new innovative technologies into the educational process, psychological analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of one's activity, improving the quality and effectiveness of one's activity, self-control, improving professional knowledge, and the ability to master the most convenient methods of working on oneself at a high level.

A teacher's psychological competence is manifested not only in their attitude towards students, but also in the organization of their personal pedagogical activity. Due to ignorance of their psychological characteristics, the teacher copies the experience of colleagues and begins to imitate them.

In this sense, it is advisable to use the following methods to improve the psychological and pedagogical competence of the teacher in the educational process. Including;

- organization of socio-psychological trainings on improving the teacher's professional skills, developing mental processes (professional memory, attention, intuition, logical thinking, etc.), forming professional knowledge, abilities, and skills, mastering psychological methods of relieving stress;

- analysis of psychological situations in order to jointly resolve issues related to professional activity (low academic performance, conflict situations in the group);
- studying at the "school for advanced training of young teachers" in order to improve the professional skills of the teacher;
- Improvement of personal qualities (skills such as analyzing one's pedagogical activity, "brainstorming," "brainstorming") that are important for a teacher to fully realize their potential in their professional activities.

One of the leading factors in the development of psychological competence is, firstly, the teacher's self-formation as a specialist, and secondly, self-awareness as a person.

The teacher's psychological and pedagogical competence is formed not uniformly, but throughout the entire professional activity. Monitoring this dynamic process allows one to adequately assess it, predict its development and the development of the teacher's personality. The teacher's personal and professional qualities are combined with their psychological competence.

Young people preparing for pedagogical activity should be aware of these characteristics.

These features of the pedagogical profession are reflected in its profессиogram.

The professional profессиogram of a teacher is expressed in the following:

- psychological characteristics of the teacher's personality;
- requirements for the psychological and pedagogical training of the teacher;
- volume and content of special training;
- content of methodological training in the specialty.

In turn, the psychological competencies of the teacher's personality are manifested in the following areas. Including;

In the ideological sphere: scientific worldview and beliefs, a deep understanding of social needs and moral necessities, a sense of social and civic duty, socio-political activity.

In the field of the teaching profession: respect for students and motivation to work with them, interest in pedagogical activity, psychological and pedagogical intelligence and observation, pedagogical tact, pedagogical imagination, organizational skills, honesty, sincerity, demandingness, decisiveness and purposefulness; restraint; self-control; professional competence.

cognitive (cognitive) sphere includes a broad scientific level, spiritual needs and interests, intellectual interest, the ability to feel the new; the desire to increase pedagogical knowledge.

For effective pedagogical activity, a teacher must possess the following types of abilities:

- cognitive ability;
- Ability to explain educational materials;
- Ability to observe;
- Speech ability;
- Organizational skills;

- Ability to gain authority;
- The ability to communicate correctly;
- The ability to see the future;
- The ability to distribute attention.

In this sense, in order to form the psychological and pedagogical competence of a teacher, it is necessary to use various psychodiagnostic methods. According to the results obtained from the psychodiagnostic data, it is necessary for the teacher to understand how they are adapting to the requirements of their professional activity and, accordingly, to further improve their pedagogical abilities.

A teacher's reputation is primarily manifested in their dedication to their profession. Only then can the teacher set an example for students through their practical activities and instill confidence in themselves. These qualities are an important factor in the education, upbringing, and professional training of young people. Indeed, awakening a sense of belonging to the fate of the Homeland, cherishing the Homeland like a place of worship, and teaching them to live with a sense of belonging to their surroundings is the sacred duty of every teacher.

References:

1. Avliyakov N.X. Modern Teaching Technology. Tashkent. 2001. 66 p.
2. Azizxujayeva N.N. Pedagogical Technology and Pedagogical Skill. TashDPU Printing House. Tashkent, 2003. 36 p.
3. Davletshin M.G. National Personnel Training Program and Main Tasks of Psychological Science. - T., 1998. - P. 3-7.
4. Karpenko L.V. Psychology. Dictionary. M., 2004.
5. Lukyanov N. I. How to Train a Professional Teacher. - M., 2012. P.17.
6. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline, and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader. - T., 2017. p. 45.
7. Markova A.K. Psychology of Professionalism. - M., International Humanitarian Fund. Knowledge. - P. 308. P.15.
8. Shodiyeva. K. Formation of innovative activity of the future teacher. T.: "Istiqlol," 2006. - 73 p.